

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

PHILOSOPHICAL FOUNDATIONS AND THE PICTURE OF THE INVESTIGATED REALITY AT HERODOTUS' "HISTORY"

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the analysis of the philosophical foundations for the creation of the first historical work in the history of mankind - "History" by Herodotus. The ontological, methodological, epistemological, logical and axiological foundations of scientific cognition, on which "the father's of history" work is based, are considered. Special attention is paid to the "picture of the investigated reality", which systematises Herodotus' ideas about the historical process. This context reveals Herodotus' understanding of historical space and historical time.

Keywords: historical science, Ancient Greece, Herodotus, worldview foundations, methodology of historical cognition, philosophical foundations, picture of the world, picture of the investigated reality, intellectual and cultural development of ancient Greece.

Herodotus' "History" organically fit into the ancient Greek culture contemporary to it, became an integral part of it. This also meant the unity of the *philosophical foundations*, on which this historical type of culture was based, and the philosophical foundations of the worldview of the author himself. Therefore, in order to understand the methodological principles of historical science developed by Herodotus and implemented in his work, it is necessary to analyse the system of these bases.

Ontological foundations.

Herodotus' general ideas about the world do not require a special and detailed description - they are quite consistent with the basic principles of Ionian philosophy. The world is holistic, unified, natural (natural). And human society as its constituent part also possesses these properties. In this regard, Herodotus breaks with the mythological worldview of logographers - the miraculous and supernatural, incomprehensible by reason was alien to him and was subject to "explanation by natural causes" [3, p. 211].

Much more interesting is his interpretation of space and time as attributes of the world and society. Before Herodotus, the description of the historical process was based on the understanding of space and time as local: historical events in separate territories were understood as unrelated, the flow of time was considered only in connection with the succession of generations within the family, dynasty [7, p. 30].

Herodotus brings to the ancient Greek tradition of historiography a fundamentally new understanding of their essential properties, already formulated and substantiated in natural philosophy. Both space and time in his understanding are internally unified; their different "parts" have common properties. Moreover, together they are also in an inseparable unity. Uniform historical events (wars, political activity) unify space. Therefore, unified space is an element of universal history [6, p. 151]; history proceeds in it. But time is also integral and unified. Therefore, the comprehensive concept of time

is another element of universal history [ibid, p. 152]; it cannot be divided into independent periods with rigid boundaries.

Methodological foundations.

The methodological foundations of Herodotus' work are based, first of all, on the ideas about the world of Ionian natural philosophy. The unified Cosmos is in constant change; everything in it is interconnected and interdependent; everything has a cause. The world is full of contradictions. There are forces opposite to each other. Their interactions lead to changes and development of the world. All these general, rationally formulated attitudes are "superimposed" on the historical process and are clearly expressed in the description of facts and events: wars between Greeks and barbarians; the presence of different religious beliefs; the existence of peoples with different customs, traditions, etc.

At the same time, in accordance with the previously mentioned philosophical ideas (the whole is not the sum of the parts; the essence of a phenomenon is determined by its general properties; the parts taken together do not yet create the essence of the system), the main attention is paid by the "father of history" to the formation of ideas about the historical process as a whole. He singles out general regularities inherent in the change of historical events in different territories, in different peoples. The main thing for him is to create a "single canvas of history" that could be covered at once, in its entirety, albeit at the expense of specific details. Some of these basic provisions were present (in the form of separate elements) in the works of his predecessors on the description of history, who on their basis comprehended the information available to them from myths, texts, oral narratives. But in Herodotus they acquire a completely different meaning, realised consistently and systematically. The whole "History" is created on this methodological basis, representing, in fact, its concrete-historical illustration.

Herodotus makes another important step in the formation of methodological foundations of historical

research. A fundamentally new component is evident in his work - the author of the "History" acts as an empiricist; he not only theorises, but also observes. Where possible, the results of these observations are generalised [3, p. 151] and conclusions are drawn on this basis. In other words, the method of induction is added to the previously prevailing deductive method. This caused a certain narrowness of the research horizon, since the results of observations limited purely rational reflections. But at the same time, this methodological attitude provided a much more objective approach to the comprehension of facts [ibid.] and, thus, significantly increased the value of Herodotus' work.

The very possibility of such a methodological transformation of the scientist was connected with the processes in the intellectual culture of Greece that took place during his lifetime. In the second half of the 5th century B.C. classical natural philosophy largely exhausted its heuristic possibilities - natural processes could be explained mainly on the basis of the formed atomistics of Leucippus - Democritus, which as if completed the "first turn" of the spiral development of philosophical knowledge. The transition to a new level of philosophical cognition of the world is provided at this time by the emergence of the Sophist schools. They "discover" that reality is not limited only to nature. There is another area, different from nature, which has its own laws of development and which also needs to be studied - knowledge itself. And this part of reality was out of the field of view of the preceding natural philosophy. A certain empirical reaction to rationalist Ionian science emerges, forming also new cognitive tools.

Gnoseological foundations.

The epistemological bases of the "History" are determined by Herodotus' solution of the following problems:

1. whether it is possible to cognise not only the events witnessed by the historian, but also the time distant from him;
2. whether the essence of the historical process is manifested in specific events;
3. what is the nature of knowledge in general.

Herodotus argues that knowledge of ancient historical events is not only possible, but also necessary. And he acts on the basis of this attitude, trying to penetrate as far into the past as possible [6, p. 151], asking about it and seeking to study all its possible aspects. Such a principled attitude, however, contained a certain internal contradiction - fantastic stories taken from mythology and relating to time immemorial had the same epistemological status as the events witnessed by Herodotus himself [3, p. 149].

The second problem is solved by Herodotus unambiguously positively. The regularities (both world and supra-world) that determine the course of history are manifested in specific events (in their sequence, in their causes, in the characters involved in them). Here the author of the "History" is a continuer of an already established tradition in ancient Greek historiography on the basis of an earlier philosophy - he recognises the presence of "manifestness" in all events and historical processes.

Knowledge - and this is clearly evident in the entire content of the History - is unified and holistic; it should not be divided. Each section, area of knowledge is necessarily connected with others and complements them. Full-fledged historical knowledge cannot exist separately from geographical, ethnographic, etc. [6, c. 152]. They seem to "flow" into each other, forming, according to Herodotus, the knowledge that should be left to posterity.

Logical foundations.

The logical foundations of Herodotus' work could not be any systematic - after all, logic as a scientific discipline did not yet exist. (Aristotle, the author of the *Organon*, the first work devoted to logic, was born a century later.) Nevertheless, one fundamentally important aspect present in the Histories must be noted. Herodotus does not unequivocally follow a chronology of events. In his description one can find manifestations of history in two hypostases: as a chronological succession of events and as a sequence subject to fundamental causality. And Herodotus allows changing the chronological sequence of events for the sake of emphasising their internal conditionality and logicity, transferring the eclipse of the Sun two years earlier so that it could be interpreted as a fatal omen before Xerxes' campaign [3, p. 41 - 42]. This seemingly obvious violation of the chronological sequence was in fact extremely important, adding another argument in favour of understanding the "History" as the first truly scientific historical work. By structuring the description in this way, Herodotus begins to move away from the associative thinking characteristic of the mythological type of worldview, realising that "after something is not because of something". Thus, he makes the first step towards the formation of a scientific-historical methodology in this direction, intuitively guessing the existence of a principle, which was later called "the unity of the historical and logical".

Axiological foundations.

The axiological foundations on which the concept of "History" is built are outlined in the introduction to it, which was quoted earlier. Therefore, it is necessary to highlight and give a brief interpretation of their main substantive aspects in more detail.

Firstly, Herodotus unequivocally asserts the value of historical knowledge in general. Knowledge about the events that took place should be collected, comprehended and preserved. What people have accomplished should be preserved; it is "worthy of being saved from oblivion" [1, p. 469].

Secondly, all peoples contribute to history. All can perform great feats [ibid]. Therefore, it is necessary to collect knowledge about the history of all peoples - only then a whole picture of the historical process will be obtained.

Thirdly, the course of the historical process is not random, but has its reasons. The present is conditioned by the past, and the past has value for the present as experience that can be utilised [ibid]. Knowledge of the past is valuable for the present as well as for the future.

In this respect, Herodotus' "History" was fundamentally different from the entire previous tradition of

ancient historiography: conceived not as a history of localities, but as a history of peoples, it not only provided contemporaries with more accurate information about the countries they knew, but also gave a key to understanding the events of the present [2, p. 12]

Fourthly, not only information about historical events that took place, but also "everything else" should be preserved, namely, legends related to prehistory. Although they are transmitted from generation to generation, perceived as legends and tales that cannot be verified, they are also valuable - they contain certain information about the past centuries. In fact, this attitude is an extrapolation of the attitude to myths in the ancient Greek intellectual tradition itself - myths are ancient history that needs to be reinterpreted.

Fifthly, the significance of each nation also means that all knowledge that relates to its history, traditions, customs, etc., should be collected and preserved, even if it appears to be untrue.

And in "History" these attitudes are consistently realised. As a result, its value has objectively increased over time, since, for example, information was recorded that the author himself characterised as incredible, but which was later confirmed.

The next basis of scientific research, which determines the construction of the corresponding scientific discipline, is the "*picture of the world*" ("*picture of the investigated reality*" [4]), which (explicitly or implicitly) is formed by a scientist as a certain model of reality, which he describes and explains. And the models of different scientists, albeit belonging to the same branch of knowledge, are inevitably different, especially at the stage of the birth of science. Let us outline a list of basic questions that will be taken into account when the scientist builds "his" "picture of the investigated reality": what are the geographical boundaries of the historical reality that the scientist considers necessary to describe; what is the time period of the description; what groups of events, factors of social life will be taken into account; on the basis of what sources this "picture of the world" will be built; how exactly the scientist will work with the available information. In addition, it is necessary to take into account the general goal orientations of the researcher, as they will also determine the general orientation of the historical narrative.

Herodotus' "Picture of the World."

Herodotus endeavors to cover in his history the entire Oikumene, all known lands, all the peoples inhabiting them, and to do so over as large a period as possible - from prehistory to contemporary events. Moreover, it should not be a description of separate territories, each of which has its own history. Herodotus builds his history on the idea of a single historical process - as a result, in his "investigated reality" there is a single geographical space, a single historical space and a single time. And everywhere there are unified laws that determine the causes and course of events. And this reality is inhabited by many peoples, each of which has its own prehistory, its own gods, customs, traditions, laws.

Such a large-scale picture of the world leads to a certain simplification of the ways of obtaining

knowledge and methods of its evaluation. Here Herodotus makes as if a step backwards in comparison with Hecateus [5, pp. 209-211], moving away from a clear orientation on the "truthfulness" of the information included in the "History". However, the volume of the presented knowledge compensates for this "shortcoming".

The geographical space of the "whole world" according to Herodotus is Europe, Africa and Asia. The author of the "History" is interested not only in the lands of Hellas (which would be obvious), but also in the territories very, very far from it, located "on the edge" of the Persian Empire of the Persian Empire. And, as already noted, he imagined the real size of the continents to be considerably smaller than they were. However, during the lifetime of the author of the "History", and significantly later, this point of view was quite fit into the existing knowledge. (Thus, a century later, Aristotle, teaching Alexander the Great, formed in him such ideas about the world, on the basis of which the latter considered it a feasible task to conquer all countries and peoples. Knowing the true size of the world at that time, he would obviously have considered it a fantasy).

The absence of rigid geographical boundaries between states and peoples is meaningfully transformed in Herodotus into the following essential characteristic of the "picture of the world" - the presence of a single historical space. In fact, the events that are common for all peoples and lands - political activity and wars - unify the space, give it additional common features from the point of view of history, and integrate the historical process. Therefore, for Herodotus, the unified space turns into a necessary element of universal history [6, p. 151]. As a result, a smaller geographical space turns into a significantly larger in scale (in terms of the number of lands and peoples) historical space.

And the same methodological approach is realised in the treatment of time as an attribute of the "picture of the world". Here the starting point of understanding time is the criticism of the works of Hecateus and the preceding logographers as a negative example for him. Herodotus moves away from tying events to genealogical connections, "demarcates the generic boundaries of history" [7, c. 30]. In the "History" he uses various chronologies (Olympiads, years of kings, years of archons, generations) available to him [6, p. 151]. For Herodotus the continuity of events was obvious, despite the fact of overlaps in chronology. Moreover, this idea dominated over various chronologies and united them [7, p. 151], became universal. As a result, another element of the universal "picture" of history was formed - a comprehensive concept of time [ibid, p. 152]. This interpretation of time determined its other scales, which fundamentally exceeded what was recorded by predecessors. Herodotus' time is epic; he does not think within the framework of reasoned dating, but uses broad temporal categories [5, p. 229], lives in the world of decades and centuries (he has practically no precise and reasoned dating). And in this time stream Herodotus allows some deviations from the actual chronology in order to emphasise the integrity, unity and regularity

of the historical process. Having built a unified historical space and time in the "History", he thus laid the foundations of universal historiography, which were later developed by Polybius [6, p. 145].

The next essential content component of Herodotus' "picture of the world" is his unambiguous and unconditional recognition of the existing global (in his understanding) impersonal laws common to the entire unified historical space-time [3, p. 41]. Herodotus constantly emphasises their manifestations in the events describing the histories of all peoples inhabiting the Oikoumene. As a result, he managed in his work to consistently realise the general philosophical and ontological attitude to understanding the cosmos as a single entity. And this fundamentally important characteristic of the "History" was highly appreciated already by ancient scholars. Thus, Dionysius of Halicarnassus (60 - 7 BC) emphasised that "...Herodotus, who touched on many different topics, created a harmonious whole." [Cited in 5, p. 385].

And, finally, characterising the picture of historical reality, recorded in "History", it is necessary to pay attention to the completeness and content of its coverage of various aspects of life of the then society. And here it turns out that the "history of mankind" in reality turned out to be the history of only certain aspects, few aspects of its life. Antique historians in general were political historians [5, p. 353]. They were interested only in wars, diplomacy. Therefore, against their background Herodotus' work is much more encyclopedic, describing various layers of life of Hellenes and "barbarians". However, even for him history is predominantly event-based, a series of wars and political events. Even Herodotus lacks anything similar to socioeconomic history or cultural history [ibid, p. 152].

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